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Muhandislik va Iqtisodiyot

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy,
innovatsion texnik,
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- 05.01.00 – Axborot texnologiyalari, boshqaruv va kompyuter grafikasi
- 05.01.01 – Muhandislik geometriyasi va kompyuter grafikasi. Audio va video texnologiyalari
- 05.01.02 – Tizimli tahlil, boshqaruv va axborotni qayta ishlash
- 05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
- 05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
- 05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
- 05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
- 05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
- 05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
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CONCEPTUAL FOUNDATIONS OF STATE REGULATION OF REGIONAL SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: The article presents the theoretical and methodological foundations of state regulation of sustainable development of regions, analyzing the imbalances and existing problems in regional development. It also describes the definitions and approaches of the “non-interventionists”, “adapters”, and “radical reformers” within the theories of state regulation of regional development. Additionally, the article outlines modern approaches to ensuring the sustainable development of regions.

Keywords: market economy, regional policy, regional development, state, regulation.

Annotatsiya: Hududlarning barqaror rivojlanishini davlat tomonidan tartibga solishning nazariy va uslubiy asoslari maqolada bayon etilgan bo'lib, unda hududiy rivojlanishdagi nomutanosibliklar va mavjud muammolar tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, mintaqaviy rivojlanishni davlat tomonidan tartibga solishga oid nazariyalarda “nointervensionalistlar”, “moslashuvchilar” va “radikal qayta o'zgartiruvchilar” yo'nalishlarining ta'riflari va yondashuvlari yoritilgan. Maqolada shuningdek, hududlarning barqaror rivojlanishini ta'minlash bo'yicha zamonaviy yondashuvlar ham keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: bozor iqtisodiyoti, mintaqaviy siyosat, hududiy rivojlanish, davlat, tartibga solish.

Аннотация: В статье изложены теоретико-методологические основы государственного регулирования устойчивого развития регионов, в которой проведен анализ диспропорций и существующих проблем регионального развития. Также в статье раскрыты определения и подходы направлений «не интервенционистов», «адаптеров» и «радикальных реформаторов» в теориях государственного регулирования регионального развития. Кроме того, в статье представлены современные подходы к обеспечению устойчивого развития регионов.

Ключевые слова: рыночная экономика, региональная политика, региональное развитие, государство, регулирование.

INTRODUCTION

For all countries of the world, regardless of their level of development, it is characteristic to have differences in resource availability, economic development, quality of life, infrastructure development, environmental conditions, and social situations. These issues can be mitigated by correctly setting and implementing the strategic and tactical goals of economic and social development in a country. In many cases, any change in a country's economic life leads either to an increase in economic efficiency or to greater social equality. If the goals are set correctly but not fully implemented, contradictions may persist or even intensify.

It is well-known that the market plays a natural regulatory role in exchange processes, ensuring its stable operation and stimulating the reproduction of all material goods necessary for human life. Alongside the market, the state plays a crucial role in regulating socio-economic processes to establish an effective economic system.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, has paid special attention to the state's role in regulating the economy, emphasizing the adoption of the "Action Strategy on Five Priority Areas for the Development of Uzbekistan in 2017–2021". The goal of the Action Strategy is "to drastically increase the effectiveness of ongoing reforms, create conditions for the comprehensive and rapid development of the state and society, modernize the country, and liberalize all spheres of life" [1].

The third priority direction of this strategic action is directly dedicated to the development and liberalization of the economy, aiming to implement innovative and efficient reforms that meet modern requirements. Sh. Mirziyoyev noted, "We have adopted and consistently implemented a number of laws, decrees, and decisions, as well as well-thought-out programs, to reorganize and further liberalize our economy on a completely new basis, improve its legal foundations, and modernize and diversify production" [2].

The primary goal of state regulation of the economy is to achieve economic and social stability, strengthen and improve the existing system, and adapt to changing conditions. Thus, the social and economic development of the country and state regulation of the economy represent a fundamental feature of modern economic systems.

In developed countries, the private sector, through market mechanisms, ensures the resolution of economic problems, including increased efficiency. However, the market can also generate political, social, and environmental issues. In addressing these challenges, the state plays a leading role in developed countries. One of the most significant directions of state policy in resolving regional socio-economic problems is the implementation of regional policy.

State regulation of the economy has been and continues to be implemented in all countries worldwide, with the state regulating the economy to varying degrees across all economic systems. The transition to a market economy and the implementation of economic reforms — restructuring property relations, material production, the labor market, and the financial market — make the state's regulatory role particularly crucial during these periods.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

In the introduction to his speech titled "The State in a Changing World", former World Bank President James D. Wolfensohn stated: "History has repeatedly demonstrated that good governance is not merely an ornament but a vital necessity. In an ineffective state, neither social nor economic sustainable development is possible" [3]. This is especially evident in countries that lack mechanisms for socio-economic self-regulation, where voluntarism flourishes unchecked, administrative skills are insufficient, and development lags behind [4].

Analyzing the economic situation in Uzbekistan's regions during the transition period suggests that both monetarist and Keynesian approaches can be applied simultaneously for effective regulation. Many scholars classify economic regulation models based on the degree of state participation into three groups:

Etatic (statist) – predominant state regulation;

Liberal – dominance of market regulators;

Mixed – a balanced combination of market and state regulators [5].

According to T.G. Morozova, the main tasks of state regulation of the economy include: economic liberalization in the initial phase of the transition period; stabilization of the economy in the second phase; and ensuring efficiency and dynamic growth in the final phase [6].

State regulation of the economy should balance interests: on the one hand, it should utilize market mechanisms for the effective implementation of economic reforms; on the other hand, it must ensure the fair distribution of incomes and resources.

Economic regulation is implemented at various levels, primarily at the national and regional levels. It can also be applied to specific industries or individual enterprises. Traditionally, state authorities and administrative bodies act as the subjects of economic regulation.

A necessary condition for overcoming stagnation in regional economic development is more extensive use of market-based self-regulation mechanisms. However, global practice shows that even well-established market economies struggle to eliminate deep-seated regional imbalances. In addressing such issues, the state plays a leading role. Political, legal, economic, social, and organizational measures should reflect the state's regulatory involvement in regional development. The implementation of such measures requires the establishment of a legal and methodological framework that provides a "unified conceptual understanding of the essence, content, and forms of state regional policy" [7].

In our view, V.N. Lexin and A.N. Shvetsov have convincingly substantiated the need for state regulation of regional development. They argue that regulating territorial (regional) development is a mandatory task for all countries worldwide. If a state neglects this responsibility, it either implies the absence of such problems (as in the Vatican), a lack of concern for its present and future, or a sign of its institutional weakness [8].

According to V.V. Kotilko, regulating regional development represents the method by which regional policy is implemented. In his view, the concept of regional development regulation is a systematic notion that should be considered as a method of substantiating ways to achieve long-term goals for regional development, as well as a tool for implementing the objectives and tasks of state regional policy at various stages of economic reform [9].

Thus, state regulation of regional development refers to a system of measures and actions aimed at ensuring the stable and balanced development of the country's territorial units to enhance economic growth and improve living standards.

In our republic, the tasks of state regulation of regional development include reducing regional disparities, encouraging the rational and efficient use of natural and economic potential, strengthening local budgets, establishing comprehensive transport, communication, and social infrastructure, and supporting regions with unfavorable ecological conditions.

The theory of state regulation of regional economic development must answer the question of which regions need to be supported by the state and whether such intervention is necessary at all. If it is necessary, the theory should also determine the methods through which the socio-economic development of selected regions can be stimulated.

This question is addressed by regional development theory. For instance, neoclassical theory explains regional economic disparities primarily by insufficient utilization of production factors. According to this theory, if these factors are fully mobilized, the level of regional economic development will eventually equalize. However, in practice, neither labor nor capital is fully mobilized, and rents are not flexible, which results in income disparities among companies and citizens across different regions [10].

At the same time, proponents of this theory do not deny the need for state intervention in the early stages of development, particularly in the form of financial assistance to address social issues in problematic regions. Nevertheless, the practical application of neoclassical theory has not confirmed its ideas: regional economic disparities were not eliminated in the short term, which made state intervention necessary.

Proponents of the cumulative growth theory argue that regional economic disparities will persist or even increase over time unless an active regional policy is implemented. They advocate for policies that aim to reduce these disparities by promoting the socio-economic development of the most underdeveloped regions. The goal is not to achieve complete equality but to narrow the gap, thereby supporting the continuous development of lagging regions.

Initially, the theory of state regulation of regional development was limited by these two opposing approaches. Later, scholars identified three distinct streams: "non-interventionists", who reject the need for state influence on regional growth; "adapters", who propose minor adjustments to spontaneous market forces by encouraging investments and labor migration; and "radical reformers" like G. Cameron, O. Grishai, G. Ioffe, and A. Treivish, who advocate for strong state intervention [11].

The essence of the "adapter" approach is that state regulation should accelerate natural processes without altering their direction. Economic growth can only be effectively stimulated if it aligns with the broader market trends that dictate the development and location of enterprises, particularly industrial ones. This scenario arises when conditions for industrial growth naturally emerge in underdeveloped regions, and the state reinforces this growth through targeted policies. If the state tries to stimulate development in regions unattractive to private investors, such efforts often prove unsuccessful.

S. Dennison and A. Loach are considered the founders of the theory of state regulation of regional development and early representatives of the "adapter" approach. They proposed two distinct conceptual approaches to regulating economic development [12].

S. Dennison can be classified as an "activist", as he advocated for state intervention to address the problem of depressed regions, a significant issue for pre-war Britain. His primary focus was on influencing the spatial distribution of industrial investments. This influence could be both direct and indirect through centralized

control over capital allocation. Although Dennison did not compare the efficiency of different forms of state influence on the localization of industrial enterprises, he noted that direct state control was more effective than investment subsidies. This was because direct control could address a broader range of issues beyond local unemployment, such as the growing agglomeration of major urban conurbations.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The article uses the methods of scientific abstraction, observation, analysis, synthesis, induction and deduction.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

We believe that the ideas of “adapters” are the most suitable for Uzbekistan. This conclusion can be justified by the following arguments. First, the approaches of “non-interventionists” have several drawbacks. For instance, the country cannot fully utilize its development potential due to inefficient resource use in certain regions. Maximizing the development potential of different regions is often one of the main objectives of regional policy. A significant portion of industrial production value and state budget revenues comes from raw-material sectors, while most mineral reserves are located in poorly developed areas with insufficient infrastructure.

Second, some sectors naturally require state involvement, particularly the development of infrastructure. The more justified the allocation of resources for these purposes, the more effective the outcomes.

The approaches of “radical reformers” are inapplicable at the current stage of development because they require budget expenditures the republic cannot afford. Regarding the assertion that stimulating economic growth in problematic regions is inefficient, it is worth noting that industrialized countries use such incentives, and they are not deemed pointless.

Although following the “adapter” model in regional policy is advisable, some regulatory measures must still be directed toward stimulating growth in the most problematic regions. This principle is largely based on the idea of “regional justice” and achieving the economic efficiency of the national economy.

Among scholars, there are two perspectives on this issue. One view suggests that there is an inverse relationship between “regional justice” and “economic efficiency”. In other words, stimulating economic growth in problematic regions inevitably reduces efficiency. Consequently, proponents of this view argue for shifting from a regional policy focused on reducing disparities to one centered on regional competition.

The second perspective asserts that “regional justice” can yield positive results. This thesis is usually supported by three arguments. First, inequality and injustice prevent the full utilization of regional development potential. Second, such policies might provide short-term benefits but lead to accumulated imbalances that later require substantial resources to correct. Third, and most importantly, significant imbalances may trigger social unrest.

Defining the goals, objectives, and methods of implementing state policy, as well as determining the state’s role in addressing social and economic challenges in regions during the transition period, remains a contentious issue.

In its most general form, the primary goal of regional policy is to modify traditional patterns of socio-economic activity, welfare distribution, and resource allocation to minimize disparities between the country’s regions.

The state influences regional development through administrative and economic instruments, using both direct and indirect regulatory measures. During the transition to a market economy, direct regulatory methods have played a significant role. These methods include financing regional development programs, key structural investment projects, and placing state orders for goods needed for national purposes through the state budget, extra budgetary funds, and centralized credit resources.

Currently, the significance of indirect regulatory methods is growing. These methods are implemented through financial and tax instruments, which create regional incentives and promote entrepreneurship across the country.

Developing comprehensive forecasts for the long-term distribution and growth of production capacity remains a critical area of state regulation of regional development, even within a market economy.

Historical and international experience demonstrates the need for extensive use of the state’s regulatory functions and responsibilities when implementing economic reforms. In all developed countries, the economy is inherently mixed, with the state fulfilling numerous coordinating functions and occasionally adopting direct regulatory measures.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, while state influence on regional socio-economic development remains necessary, future growth should primarily rely on market mechanisms. However, during the transition period, it is crucial not to rely solely on the self-regulating mechanisms of an underdeveloped market.

In Uzbekistan, market institutions have not yet fully covered all areas of economic relations in the complex market environment. Therefore, the state must actively participate in the reform process until effective self-regulating market mechanisms are established. At the same time, the state should support the formation of new market institutions, particularly in the regions. Only when stable and effective market mechanisms are in place will it be possible to ensure sustainable economic growth and implement structural changes without direct state intervention.

List of references

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2017-yil 7-fevraldagi "O'zbekiston Respublikasini yanada rivojlantirish bo'yicha Harakatlar strategiyasi to'g'risida"gi PF-4947-son Farmoni. <https://lex.uz/docs/3107036>.
2. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoyevning Oliy Majlisga Murojaatnomasi. // "Xalq so'zi", 2017 yil 23 dekabr.
3. The State in a Changing World Bank. Oxford University Press. 2019. P. Lii.
4. Эльянов А. Государство и развитие. // Мировая экономика и международные отношения. 2023. № 1. 3-б.
5. Regional Problems of the Transitional Economy. Moscow: Ekonomika. 2018. P. 611.
6. Государственное регулирование экономики. М.: ЮНИТИ. 2001. С. 12-13.
7. Lexin V., Shvetsov A. Regional Policy of Russia: Concepts, Problems, Solutions. Article Ten: The Meaning and Mechanisms of State Regulation of Territorial Development // Russian Economic Journal. 2019. No. 4. P. 35.
8. Региональные проблемы переходной экономики. М.: Экономика. 2020. С. 611.
9. Государственное регулирование экономики. М.: ЮНИТИ. 2021. С. 12-13.
10. Котилко В.В. Региональная экономическая политика. М.: Издательство РДЛ, 2001. С.25.
11. Гутман Г.В., Мироедов А.А., Федин С.В. Управление региональной экономикой. М. Финансы и статистика. 2002. С.20.
12. Kuznetsov O. The Theoretical Foundations of State Regulation of Regional Economic Development // Voprosy Ekonomiki, 2022, No. 4, p. 62.

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